

Prototype Instrumented Drifter	Qty: 15	<i>To be assembled</i>
Bill of Materials	Date: 12/9/2021	AV

#	Qty per	Component	Alt	Part information (description)	manufacturer	Manufacturer part #	Part information (manufacturer)	Misc.
1	1	MICROCONTROLLER	TEENSY		PJRC	Teensy 3.2	PJRC Teensy 4.0	
2	1	GPS		Sensor	Adafruit	PA1010D	Mini GPS PA1010D	
3	1	IMU		Sensor	Pimoroni	ICM20948	Pimoroni ICM20948	
4	1	MICROSD BREAKOUT	SD CARD READER	Writes collected data to microSD	Pololu	2597	Pololu microSD Breakout Board #2597	
5	1	BATTERY			EEMB	502030	EEMB 3.7V Li-ion 502030	
6	1	LED		Status indicator - 2-pin LED	/	/	/	
7	1	RESISTOR		For LED	/	/	/	
8	1	CONNECTOR (MALE)	JST MALE	Used in battery-switch circuit	/	/	JST-PH 2.0	
9	2	CONNECTOR (FEMALE)	JST FEMALE					
10	1	SWITCH		Located in battery circuit, operates sensor through watertight enclosure	ITW	48-2-RB-N-RD-B	ITW 48-2-RB-N-RD-B	
11	1	PLA PIECE 1	INTERNAL SCAFFOLD	Holds SD card reader in place internally, as well as PLA pieces 2 and 3 in place internally.	Incept3D	/	/	Custom
12	1	PLA PIECE 2	TEENSY PLATE	Holds microcontroller in place internally	Incept3D	/	/	Custom
13	1	PLA PIECE 3	GPS-IMU PLATE	Holds GPS and IMU in place internally	Incept3D	/	/	Custom